

APPENDIX D
Action Log Example

12:08:03 Player 0 is going right from (-20.47,-43.9401)
12:08:04 Player 2 is going right from (-19.736,-43.94174)
12:08:11 Player 0 is going right from (-18.34056,-43.9401)
12:08:12 Player 2 is going right from (-18.36893,-43.94174)
12:08:12 Player 0 is going right from (-16.051,-43.9401)
12:08:13 Player 1 is going right from (-20.13,-43.94174)
12:08:13 Player 1 is going left from (-19.24194,-43.94174)
12:08:14 Player 2 is going right from (-15.09915,-43.94174)
12:08:14 Player 1 jumped from (-20.31115,-43.94174)
12:08:14 Player 1 is going right from (-20.31115,-42.88129)
12:08:15 Player 2 is going right from (-13.36335,-43.94174)
12:08:15 Player 0 is going right from (-16.04792,-43.9401)
12:08:15 Player 0 is going right from (-16.04177,-43.9401)
12:08:15 Player 1 attacked
12:08:15 Player 0 is going right from (-16.03561,-43.9401)
12:08:15 Player 0 is going right from (-16.01631,-43.9401)
12:08:15 Player 0 is going right from (-15.95362,-43.9401)
12:08:16 Player 2 attacked
12:08:16 Player 1 used his power
12:08:16 Player 0 is going right from (-15.03481,-43.9401)
12:08:17 Player 2 is going left from (-10.42481,-43.94174)
12:08:17 Player 2 attacked
12:08:17 Player 1 is going right from (-19.52016,-43.94174)
12:08:18 Player 2 attacked
12:08:18 Player 0 used his power
12:08:18 Player 2 is going right from (-11.63062,-43.94174)
12:08:18 Player 2 attacked
12:08:19 Player 2 attacked
12:08:19 Player 0 is going right from (-7.62048,-43.9401)
12:08:19 Player 0 jumped from (-7.563948,-43.9401)
12:08:19 Player 0 is going right from (-7.521948,-43.64953)
12:08:19 Player 2 attacked
12:08:20 Player 2 attacked
12:08:20 Player 0 jumped from (-5.473409,-43.94174)